

SURFACE AND BULK POROSITY IN OUT-OF-AUTOCLAVE PREPREGS

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ABSTRACT

In composites manufacturing both bulk and surface porosity are undesirable outcomes that should be minimized or eliminated. Bulk porosity negatively impacts mechanical properties whereas surface porosity produces an uneven and aesthetically displeasing exterior. In prepreg processing, out-of-autoclave processes have a greater tendency to exhibit problems with porosity relative to autoclave processes due to the lower compaction pressures. This has led to a greater emphasis on gas removal prior to cure and more stringent requirements on high vacuum levels during processing. The formation, evolution, and removal of voids in OOA prepregs currently lack a robust scientific understanding. The present study aims to investigate the evolution of bulk and surface porosity due to dissolved volatiles, as well as the relationship between them and drivers behind them. Flat, fully evacuated laminates were cured under various processing conditions and their bulk porosity after cure was quantified by density and thickness measurements. Using a transparent glass tool and a video camera connected to a digital microscope, the tool-laminate interface was optically recorded in-situ during cure. Based on observations of resin flow and wetting, bubble movement, and bubble growth at the tool-laminate interface from the recorded video, an understanding of porosity drivers and mechanisms is developed. Process parameters considered in the study include resin pressure, resin moisture content and prepreg fiber architecture.

1 INTRODUCTION

In composites manufacturing the presence of porosity in finished parts is an undesirable outcome that is garnering considerable attention. Despite this, the fundamental mechanisms governing the formation and evolution of porosity are still poorly understood. The standard industrial solution to porosity in prepreg processing is to apply considerable pressure to the part using an autoclave to shrink bubbles and keep volatiles in solution. Out-of-autoclave (OOA) manufacturing eliminates the need for the autoclave, but exacerbates the porosity problem by limiting the available pressure to atmospheric. Because of this, OOA processes rely more on gas extraction prior to cure to ensure parts with acceptable porosity levels. Modern OOA prepregs are partially impregnated with resin to provide breathability and allow gas evacuation within the laminate prior to resin flow and consolidation. Studies have been performed on in-plane and through thickness permeability and gas evacuation on OOA prepregs throughout the debulk and cure cycles [1,2].

Surface porosity, the presence of voids on the exterior surface of a part, provides an additional challenge to composites manufacturing. Currently, little information can be found in the literature on surface porosity. Unlike bulk porosity, surface porosity has only a minor effect on bulk mechanical properties. Instead surface porosity produces a pock-marked exterior that is both uneven and aesthetically displeasing. In some manufacturing sectors surface porosity can also prevent composite parts from meeting aero/hydro-dynamic requirements. Figure 1 shows an image of a laminate with severe surface

porosity. Surface porosity is most commonly seen on the mould side, the side of the part which manufacturers frequently use as a product exterior due to the even and attractive finish that can be achieved. Post production repairs are both cost and labour intensive and therefore understanding the causes of surface porosity is industrially relevant.

Figure 1: Surface porosity (black) on a small, flat prepreg laminate.

The elimination of voids relies on successfully removing the gases from the voids and channels initially present in the laminate, completely infiltrating those spaces with resin during the early part of the cure cycle, and preventing void growth caused by the presence of moisture or other volatiles dissolved in the resin. This requires several processes to occur in a particular sequence:

1. Gas initially present in the laminate must be removed. This is done by applying vacuum to the laminate and allowing adequate time for the air to flow out of the part and to be removed by the vacuum system. Resin viscosity needs to be high during this process so the vacuum channels remain open.
2. The evolution of new gas within the material through vaporization of volatiles must be suppressed. This can be achieved by ensuring the pressure in the resin exceeds the vapour pressure of any volatiles at all times during processing.
3. The resin must flow into the spaces previously occupied by gas. This occurs when resin viscosity is low, void pressure is low, and resin pressure is high.

In the case of a resin containing no volatiles, a fully evacuated laminate need only have the resin fill in the empty space to produce a porosity free laminate. The objective of the current study is to develop an understanding of porosity drivers in fully evacuated laminates. Therefore we focus our attention on step 2 above. Both surface and bulk porosity are quantified and the relation between them discussed.

It is important to identify differences between ply-tool and ply-ply interfaces. A ply in the bulk of the laminate is in contact with two neighbouring plies both generally having in-plane and through thickness permeabilities, gas evacuation pathways and elastic compliance. A ply in contact with a tool has only one neighbour with these characteristics as tools, generally, are rigid, impermeable boundaries often made of a material dissimilar to the composite. To further complicate matters some modern OOA prepregs have a resin film on one side only, and so the choice of which side to place in contact with the tool is also an important consideration. Surface energetics, wetting kinetics, roughness, surface contaminants and release agent are all factors which will likely influence the composite surface behaviour; however, the precise nature of their influence on surface porosity is currently unknown.

2 PARAMETER SELECTION

Porosity management is a balance between void sources and void sinks. Void sources include entrapped air, vaporization of dissolved volatiles and reaction by-products, and incomplete resin infiltration. OOA resin systems cure via an addition polymerization reaction to minimize reaction by-products. Epoxies are hygroscopic materials and can absorb of the order of 1 wt% moisture. This can be a significant source of voids as vaporizing moisture undergoes a significant volumetric expansion. Moisture can increase in significance as a void source by increasing the concentration of dissolved moisture (increased activity) and/or by increasing the temperature (increased equilibrium vapour pressure).

Resin pressure is an important parameter that has been investigated by multiple authors [7,8,9]. Resin pressure directly resists the expansion of bubbles within the resin and reducing resin pressure allows bubble expansion by ideal gas and dissolved volatile evaporation mechanisms. The consolidation pressure applied to the laminate is born by the resin and the fiber bed together; whatever pressure is not carried by the fiber bed manifests as resin pressure. The fiber bed effective stress is a function of the stiffness behaviour of the fiber bed and the fiber volume fraction [10]. In OOA manufacturing the consolidation pressure is, ideally, 1 atm however the actual resin pressure is always less than this. Resin pressure may be reduced by applying a lower vacuum level (e.g. applying a vacuum of only 0.8 atm gauge pressure instead of 1 atm) and/or by promoting resin bleed [7,8]. Net-resin pre-preg systems are designed to be processed with little or no resin bleed; however, redistribution of resin in the laminate can still increase the local fiber volume fraction thereby increasing its ability to take load and reduce the resin pressure. It has been shown that in configured structures resin bleed into pockets caused by caul sheets and ply drops can increase the porosity locally [11].

Tests for the current study were designed such that nearly all of the entrapped air in the laminates is removed in order to isolate and determine how and under what conditions dissolved volatiles, mainly moisture, develop into porosity. Referring to the steps presented in the introduction, the present study focuses on step 2: evolution of dissolved volatiles. Figure 2 outlines the test parameters relative to a porosity free baseline. The baseline laminates were conditioned at 33% relative humidity (RH) and cured at 1 atm of consolidation pressure. Care was taken to minimize the amount of resin bleed in the baseline laminates. One parameter was changed in every test with the intent of activating a porosity inducing mechanism (discussed above). Increased moisture content laminates were conditioned at 75% RH, reduced consolidation pressure laminates were subjected to 2/3, 1/3 or 0/3 atm consolidation pressure, and the higher cure temperature laminates were ramped to 180°C instead of 120°C.

Figure 2: Schematic test plan for the current study.

3 METHODS AND MATERIALS

The material used in this study was Cytec MTM45-1 5HS, an OOA prepreg designed to allow for a flexible curing cycle [5]. The prepreg consists of a resin film on one side (henceforth known as the resin rich side) that has partially impregnated the carbon fabric. The 5HS fiber mat is made from 6K IM7 carbon fiber tows that measure approximately 2mm in width and 8mm in length between crimps.

Laminates used in this study were 10cm x 10cm x 4 plies and debulk times were 5-10 min prior to heat up and cure. The cure cycle used was a 1.5°C/min ramp to 120°C followed by a hold for 4 hours. The small laminate size allows complete air evacuation prior to resin flow while maintaining the moisture content of the resin. In order to evaluate the effect of resin pressure laminates were subjected the reduced consolidation pressure or resin bleed. Reduction of the consolidation pressure was achieved using a double vacuum bag system and a rigid aluminum bridge placed across the laminate, as depicted in Figure 3. The primary vacuum bag is under full vacuum while the secondary vacuum bag is set to the desired consolidation pressure. Atmospheric pressure is supported by the aluminum bridge in the secondary vacuum bag. Various degrees of resin bleed was facilitated by adding either 2 or 5 layers of peel ply between the laminate and the release film. Moisture content was varied by conditioning laminates at a higher relative humidity. In order to observe the evolution of the laminate surface in-situ, each laminate was laid up and cured on a 6 mm thick borosilicate glass tool and video micrographs were recorded using a Keyence VHX-1000 digital microscope. Figure 4 shows a representative image of a laminate in-situ. Two types of surface porosity have been identified: voids residing in the inter-tow channels (figure 4b red) and dry fiber tows (figure 4b blue).

Figure 3: Reduced consolidation pressure experimental setup.

Figure 4: a) In-situ laminate surface b) Same image with voids and dry, uninfiltated fiber tows selected.

Surface porosity on laminates can be viewed and quantified using image analysis. Surface voids tend to be rough and so reflect light diffusely whereas other regions of the part's surface are smooth and

produce a specular reflection. Figure 1 is an example of an image captured using this method. Images were analyzed using ImageJ image analysis software. Laminates were subsequently cut and bulk porosity was quantified using both density and thickness measurements.

4 RESULTS AND OBSERVATIONS

Figure 5 shows the surface evolution of a baseline laminate. Within the first 10 minutes of the temperature ramp (1.5°C/min) the resin pools wet the glass tool. Resin is seen to arrive at the surface through the pinholes and flow in the inter-tow channels, consistent with previous studies [12]. The inter-tow channels are filled at approximately 24 minutes. After this the resin begins infiltrating the intra-tow channels. Complete infiltration occurs at approximately 66 minutes into the cure cycle which will be used as a benchmark for comparison. Baseline laminates show no bubble formation or surface porosity, indicating that the resin pressure is adequate to keep any volatiles (moisture) in solution. The results also suggest that all air was removed during the vacuum debulk and that there was sufficient resin pressure and low enough resin viscosity to completely fill all void spaces prior to resin gelation.

Figure 5: In-situ surface evolution of a baseline laminate.

The effect of consolidation pressure on porosity development was evaluated next. Figure 6 shows bulk and surface porosity on reduced consolidation pressure laminates and the corresponding in-situ images of these laminates at the 66 minute point (time when the baseline laminate is fully infiltrated). Laminates cured under 2/3 atm showed minimal porosity and no bubble growth was observed. However the 8 mm surface fiber tows contain dry spots at their centers suggesting that the lower consolidation pressure resulted in a lower resin pressure and therefore a smaller driving force for resin infiltration. Laminates cured at 1/3 atm showed significant surface porosity and minor bulk porosity. During the cure, resin bubbles are seen to appear and move through the resin toward dry fiber tows and be evacuated (consistent with observations by Gangloff and Cender [13]), shown in Figure 7. These gas bubbles are transported by resin advection and the pressure gradient in the resin due to Darcy flow. It is believed that each laminate has the same resin bubble content and that bubbles in the 1/3 atm laminates are bigger due to ideal gas expansion. At approximately 40 minutes into cure the inter-tow channels are filled, resin begins to infiltrate the tows and thus flow is severely reduced. The bubbles become stagnant and are seen to grow over time, figure 8. Bubbles are consistently seen to grow from small, pre-existing bubbles and, conversely, regions without pre-existing bubbles show no bubble growth. This suggests that bubble nucleation is not a factor in surface porosity. Resin flow was much slower than for the baseline and

slower than the 2/3 atm laminates confirming a further reduction in resin pressure. The 8 mm fiber tows each contain a dry spot in their center due to insufficient infiltration. Laminates cured under zero consolidation pressure (0/3 atm) showed significant bulk and surface porosity. No resin flow is seen until bubbles begin growing. At approximately 25 minutes (~62°C) into cure, the resin viscosity is low enough (~560 Pa-s) that bubble growth is observed. At first the bubbles grow slowly since the resin viscosity is still high but further into the cure cycle when the viscosity is lower the bubbles grow quite rapidly and in some cases evacuate through the fiber tows. At 75 minutes bubble growth stops, likely due to depletion of moisture in the resin.

Figure 6: Top: Reduced consolidation pressure quantified porosity, bottom: in-situ images at 66 minutes a) 2/3 atm b) 1/3 atm c) 0/3 atm.

Figure 7: Bubble transport and evacuation in a 1/3 atm consolidation pressure laminate, bubble of interest is circled.

Figure 8: Bubble stagnation and growth in a 1/3 atm consolidation pressure laminate.

When reducing the consolidation pressure, both the fiber bed stress and the resin pressure are reduced. To isolate the effect of resin pressure, resin was allowed to bleed into peel plies while consolidation pressure was held constant. Figure 9 shows the measured porosity for the resin bleed tests and an in-situ image at 66 min into cure of a laminate cured with 5 layers of peel ply. Laminates cured with 2 layers of peel ply lost approximately 13% resin content and showed surface behaviour identical to the baseline; no porosity and fiber tows fully infiltrated. The reduction in resin pressure was insufficient to cause porosity. Laminates cured with 5 layers of peel ply lost approximately 27% resin content and have significant bulk and surface porosity. Up to approximately 50 min into cure the laminates show behaviour consistent with the baseline but afterwards bubbles begin to grow with time and resin flow in the intra-tow channels is seen to slow down. Both observations are consistent with decreasing resin pressure due to resin bleed. The 8 mm fiber tows each contain dry spots in their centers as a result of the drop in resin pressure.

Figure 9: Left: Quantified bulk and surface porosity for bleed tests, right: 5 peel ply bleed laminate at 66 min.

The effect of absorbed moisture was evaluated next. Figure 10 shows the measured porosity for the increased moisture content tests and an in-situ image at 66 min into cure. These laminates show minor bulk porosity (consistent with Grunenfelder [4]) and very minor surface porosity. The surface evolution was identical to the baseline; no observed bubble growth and laminates were fully infiltrated at approximately 66 min.

Figure 10: Left: Quantified bulk and surface porosity for increased moisture content tests, right: 75% RH laminate at 66 min.

Increasing the cure hold temperature to 180°C had no impact on porosity development. Each laminate fully infiltrated and had zero bulk and surface porosity. An explanation for this result is presented in the discussion.

5 DISCUSSION

The results provide strong evidence that both surface and bulk porosity are in part directly related to insufficient resin pressure. The consequences of compromising resin pressure as a void sink are clearly shown in figure 6. This is not to say that moisture content is not a factor but rather resin pressure is the barrier that moisture must overcome to cause porosity. Using a river dam analogy, resin pressure is the dam and moisture content is the water level. Water level exceeding the dam height will cause spillage but not nearly as much as if the dam broke.

A bubble in the uncured resin at room temperature is essentially a micro-environment where dissolved volatiles can vapourize and diffuse but cannot be evacuated. Applying vacuum will have little effect on resin bubbles because the high resin viscosity will prevent ideal gas expansion and the volatiles will already be in equilibrium with their vapours at the bubble interface. Applying a temperature ramp greatly alters the state of bubbles. Bubbles can grow via ideal gas expansion as the resin viscosity reduces; the pressure drop in the bubble may reduce the increasing volatile vapour pressure below equilibrium. Bubbles are transported advectively by the resin and by pressure gradient driven Darcy flow towards the resin flow front, possibly being evacuated through the fiber tows. When macro resin flow (inter-tow channel flow) ceases the bubbles will stagnate and if the equilibrium volatile vapour pressure exceeds that of the hydrostatic resin pressure, unstable bubble growth will occur up to gelation or sufficient volatile depletion. Figure 11 plots the well-known moisture diffusion based bubble growth criterion developed by Kardos [4,6]. Several levels of initial moisture content (represented by initial relative humidity) are plotted. According to the criterion, bubbles will grow only if the internal bubble pressure due to moisture, indicated by the different curves, exceeds the resin pressure. Marked on the plot are the porosity and porosity free zones and assumed resin profiles for various tests in this study. As a rough approximation we may take resin pressure to be about half of the consolidation pressure. Some tests are well predicted by figure 11; 1/3 consolidation pressure and 5 peel ply bleed both cross the 33% RH curve and enter the porosity zone and both tests show time dependent bubble growth. However some

tests are predicted to develop porosity and show none. The curves predict that the baseline tests are just barely crossing into the porosity zone, yet no porosity manifested in any baseline laminate. As well, the curves predict the 75% RH laminate crossing into the porosity zone at roughly the same temperature as the 1/3 consolidation pressure tests at 33% RH yet the 75% RH laminates are nearly porosity free.

Kardos' derivation assumes the bulk moisture content is constant. However it has been shown that a laminate containing moisture can be dried by a vacuum although the time scale is longer than for air evacuation [3]. During the temperature ramp the bulk moisture content decreases due to diffusion and evolution of moisture into the gaseous phase, which can be represented as a reduction in the initial RH conditioning. A first order estimate (non-dimensionalized Fick's 2nd law ignoring concentration gradients) of the reduction in bulk moisture due to drying during the first 40 minutes of cure is 8% RH for laminates conditioned at 33% RH. Plotted on Figure 11 is the curve for 25% RH; this curve correctly predicts porosity manifestation for all laminates conditioned at 33% RH. The same reasoning applied to the 75% RH tests helps explain their lack of porosity. This model is simply a criterion that represents the upper bound of moisture diffusion based bubble growth; resin pressure above the initial RH curve (ignoring drying) will suppress moisture diffusion based bubble growth since the curves can only reduce from drying. Therefore assuming bulk moisture content is constant represents a conservative estimate. The 33% RH curve predicts the minimum permissible resin pressure for a porosity free laminate to be just above 0.5 atm at 120°C corresponding to a consolidation pressure of just above 1 atm. Therefore in order to never enter the porosity zone a laminate must contain, at most, an initial moisture content corresponding to a 33% RH environment. Being a criterion, this model gives no quantitative indication for porosity. There are other drivers for porosity than resin pressure such as air evacuation and resin infiltration. Timing of events and evolution of resin properties must therefore be considered in a quantitative porosity model.

Figure 11: Moisture bubble growth map with assumed resin pressure profiles for various tests (porosity zones are distinguished by the coloured curves).

Significant resin bleed has also been shown to compromise the effectiveness of resin pressure as a void sink. Increased fiber volume fraction due to resin bleed enhances the fiber bed's ability to carry load; if the fiber volume fraction reaches a critical value then the resin pressure will always be low despite how

much pressure is applied. A sufficient reduction in resin pressure will allow moisture diffusion bubble growth to occur as shown in figure 11 (note the resin pressure profile shown is an assumed, qualitative profile). This mechanism can occur locally and/or globally, depending on the situation causing the resin to bleed. Configured structures that use caul sheets, ply drops, gaps, etc. introduce pockets into which resin can flow. Therefore care must be taken to ensure maximum consolidation pressure is applied and that the design of a composite part disallows or minimizes resin bleed in net-resin pre-preg systems.

Increasing the cure hold temperature to 180°C produced a porosity free laminate contrary to the prediction of the bubble growth criterion in figure 11. Considering the timing of events provides a potential explanation for this unexpected result. Ignoring drying, bubble growth is predicted to occur at approximately 115°C (~62 min into cure) but by this point the laminate is fully infiltrated. Figure 12a shows the laminate surface at the time of satisfying the criterion. The bubble growth criterion is satisfied however no bubble growth was observed. This could be due to that the bubbles are immersed in an incompressible fluid within a low permeability fiber bed and therefore cannot easily displace the resin. In addition, at this point in the cure cycle the resin is beginning to cure and the viscosity is starting to increase. This may result in a higher external pressure on bubbles causing them not to grow. The 75% RH and 1/3 consolidation laminates (figure 12b and 12c respectively) both enter the porosity zone at roughly the same temperature (assuming constant bulk moisture content) however, at this point the 75% RH laminate is more infiltrated due to the higher resin pressure. Being almost fully infiltrated, bubble growth in the 75% RH laminate is limited to a very small amount while the 1/3 consolidation pressure laminate is far from being fully infiltrated and bubbles can freely grow and displace resin. The 5 peel ply bleed laminate (figure 12d) also satisfies the criterion around this time and has a similar degree of infiltration as the 75% RH laminates however the resin pressure is plummeting due to resin bleed and infiltration rate significantly reduces. This gives the system time for bubbles to grow and displace resin into the uninfiltrated tows. It is important to remember that in figure 12 the latter two laminates have considerably lower resin pressure than the former two.

Figure 12: Point during cure when the bubble growth criterion is satisfied assuming constant bulk moisture content for a) Increased temperature b) 75% RH c) 1/3 atm consolidation d) 5 peel ply bleed.

In situations where significant porosity manifests surface porosity is commonly seen in greater quantity than bulk porosity. Figure 13 is a plot of surface versus bulk porosity for the present study. Many of tests did not develop significant porosity and are clustered around the origin. The non-zero data points all fall above the 1:1 line showing surface porosity to be greater than bulk porosity. The relationship is monotonic; however, more data is required to substantiate a trend.

Figure 13: Surface versus bulk porosity.

6 CONCLUSION

Drivers of surface and bulk porosity were investigated in small laminates that were evacuated of entrapped air but contain dissolved volatiles (water). A cure cycle that allows for complete resin infiltration was used. In this processing regime the only sources of porosity are the dissolved volatiles; based on this, resin pressure, moisture content and cure temperature were hypothesized as possible parameters influencing porosity. Decreasing resin pressure produced minimal porosity up to a threshold past which the loss of resin pressure produced considerable amounts of surface and bulk porosity. Significant loss of resin pressure by means of lower consolidation pressure and resin bleed both produced considerable porosity. Visual observation of porosity evolution suggests that all bubble growth originates from small, pre-existing bubbles in the resin. Increasing the content of dissolved moisture in laminates produced a minor increase in surface and bulk porosity. Increasing the cure temperature did not affect porosity, contrary to expectations. A possible explanation is that the laminate, at the point when moisture based bubble growth can occur, is fully infiltrated and bubbles cannot grow due to the inability to displace the resin.

A moisture diffusion based bubble growth criterion developed by Kardos is used to explain the results in this study. Kardos' derivation assumes constant bulk moisture content and it was shown that consideration of partial resin drying during the cure cycle gave a good agreement between theory and experimental results. The bubble growth criterion delineates the regime where moisture diffusion based bubble growth is possible and represents an upper bound since resin drying can only reduce the pressure inside the bubbles. No quantitative predictions are given by this criterion; it is suggested that the timing of events and evolution of resin properties during the cure cycle are important considerations alongside this criterion.

All tests in this study that developed significant porosity consistently show much greater surface porosity than bulk porosity. Further research is required to elucidate the mechanism(s) responsible for this behaviour.

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